

Targeted inactivation of gamma-synuclein gene affects anxiety and exploratory behaviour of mice

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Gamma (γ) synuclein is a member of the family of synucleins, which are cytoplasmic, predominantly, neuronal, proteins found only in vertebrates. Significant quantities of γ -synuclein are found in the axons and presynaptic terminals of neurons located in brain areas responsible for forming emotions and memory. However, the involvement of γ -synucleins in controlling neuronal and synaptic processes underlying various types of behavior in humans and animals have not yet been studied. We provide the first demonstration that the absence of γ -synuclein increases orientational-investigative activity in a novel context and decreases the level of situational anxiety in animals.

Keywords: γ -synuclein, knockout, mouse, genetically modified animals, anxiety, behavior.

Synucleins are proteins mainly expressed in the nervous system and located in presynaptic terminals. The role of synucleins in the functioning of the nervous system remains unclear, though changes in the structure of these proteins due to mutations or post-translational modifications, as well as abnormalities in their production and/or degradation, have been shown to lead to the appearance of a variety of pathologies [8, 13, 21, 27]. The synuclein family consists of three proteins with similar overall molecular structures and extremely high levels of homology in their N-terminal amino acid sequences. The gene encoding the precursor protein of the synuclein family evidently arose at the early stages of vertebrate evolution, while two sequential duplications of extensive regions of the genome and their subsequent divergence led to the appearance of three different synuclein-encoding genes in the genomes of most current vertebrates [1, 2].

The first member of the family, α -synuclein, was identified as a protein with a predominantly synaptic localization in neurons in the electric ray. Subsequent studies identified the other two members of the family – β -synuclein and γ -synuclein – and demonstrated that the localization in presynaptic terminals of mature neurons is typical of all synucleins in all vertebrate species studied [7, 14, 29]. However, in most embryonic neurons, synucleins are located in the cell body and it is only in the late embryonic and early postnatal periods that, along with changes in the level of expression, there are changes in intracellular localization. The three synucleins have different but overlapping expression profiles in the nervous system. The levels of expression of α -synuclein and β -synuclein are particularly high in the neurons of evolutionarily young sections of the nervous system, while γ -synuclein is expressed at a high level in the sensory neurons of the peripheral nervous system, in spinal cord motoneurons, and certain groups of neurons in the brain [20].

The significant interest of researchers and clinicians in the synuclein family arises primarily because of the well documented relationship between changes in the structure

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and/or increased levels of expression of α -synuclein, leading to aggregation, on the one hand, and the etiology and pathogenesis of Parkinson's disease on the other. However, it remains unclear how changes in the metabolism of α -synuclein induces the molecular-cellular mechanisms leading to the development of pathological processes in the nervous system [8, 13]. The many lines of transgenic mice overexpressing different versions of this protein allow only some aspects of the pathology typical of synucleinopathy to be modeled [8]. It should be noted that although convincing evidence for the direct involvement of γ -synuclein in the pathogenesis of neurological diseases in humans has not yet been obtained, the pathological changes (formation of specific protein deposits and the death of certain neuron types) in mice overexpressing this protein are extremely similar to those in mice overexpressing α -synuclein under control of the same (Thy1) promoter [22].

Mouse strains obtained by targeted genomic modification leading to complete inactivation of one of the synucleins (knockout animals) are of particular value for studies of the normal function of synucleins. Several laboratories have produced and characterized strains of α -, β -, and γ -synuclein knockout mice [3, 10, 21]. All these animals are viable, fertile, and show no marked phenotypic changes or obvious (detectable without instrumental analyses) behavioral impairments. Loss of one of the synucleins can produce elevated resistance of certain neuron populations in young animals to the effects of a variety of neurotoxins. For example, dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra of mice with inactivation of γ -synuclein or α -synuclein are more resistant to the neurotoxin MPTP (1-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyridine) than the same neurons in wild-type mice [12, 24]. At the same time, neither the dopamine level nor the reuptake of this neurotransmitter by presynaptic terminals in the striatum of knockout animals showed any difference from values in wild-type animals, which may be due to functional compensation by the other two members of the synuclein family [24, 25].

Studies of the activity of knockout animals in the open field and home cage tests showed that the behavior of mice with double knockout of α -synuclein and γ -synuclein corresponds to the behavior typical of animals with elevated levels of activity of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra, while the activity of mice with knockout of only one of these genes was no different from that of wild-type mice. However, in elderly knockout animals, knockout of α -synuclein led to a significant decrease in the DA level in the striatum and, as a result, the development of impaired synaptic transmission. In the case of loss of γ -synuclein, these age-related changes were not seen [4]. Overall, experimental data obtained to date provide evidence that α -synuclein is actively involved in regulating neurotransmission in dopaminergic synapses, while γ -synuclein has a very restricted role in this process. The role of γ -synuclein in other types of neuronal synapses, including those whose

Fig. 1. Analysis of animals' behavior in the "novel cage" test. Minute-by-minute dynamics of investigative activity (number of rearings) in the test animals. WT – control group with the normal unmodified γ -synuclein gene, $\gamma^{-/-}$ – animals with knockout of the γ -synuclein gene. * $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$ (Student's t test).

functions determine different types of behavior in humans and animals, remains unstudied.

The aim of the present work was to study behavioral characteristics in genetically modified mice with homozygous inactivating mutations of the γ -synuclein gene (γ -synuclein knockout mice).

METHODS

Animals. The construction and characterization of γ -synuclein gene knockout mice have been described elsewhere [21]. The present experiments were performed using mice with the C57BL/6J genetic background. Control animals without genome modification and genetically modified animals carrying a mutation inactivating the γ -synuclein gene originated from the same ancestor as used in creating the γ -synuclein knockout mouse strain. Colonies of these animals were kept in parallel in identical conditions.

All experiments were performed using males aged three months and weighing 22–24 g. Throughout the experimental period, the animals were kept individually in cages at a temperature of 22°C with a natural 12-h light cycle. Analysis of the genotypes of the experimental animals and documentation of results were performed as described previously [21].

Behavioral tests. Immediately before each test, all surfaces of the apparatus coming into contact with the experimental animals were washed with water, rinsed with 70% ethanol, and dried. Each experimental group consisted of 10 animals unless otherwise stated.

The novel cage test. The mouse was carefully placed in the center of a cage of size 21.5 × 27.5 cm and the number of vertical rearings was counted over a period of 5 min.

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Fig. 2. Analysis of animals' behavior in the dark-light chamber. *a*) Latent period of excursions by mice into the light sector; *b*) number of excursions into the light sector; *c*) total time spent in the light sector. $**p < 0.01$. For further details see caption to Fig. 1.

Fig. 3. Analysis of animals' behavior in the O-shaped elevated maze. *a*) Latent period of excursions by animals into the unenclosed sector of the maze (sec); *b*) number of excursions into the unenclosed segment (excursions); *c*) total time spent by mice in the unenclosed sector. For further details see caption to Figs. 1 and 2.

The test was performed in an open cage in conditions of natural illumination at 50 Lx [18, 28].

Dark-light chamber. A chamber consisting of two sectors – a dark sector of 15 × 21 cm with a roof and a light sector of 31 × 21 cm, connected by a corridor of size 6.5 × 6.5 cm and length 6 cm, at floor level, was used. The light sector was illuminated at a level of 150 Lx. The mouse was placed in the dark sector and the following parameters were recorded for 5 min: the latent period for departure of all paws into

the light sector, the number of excursions, and the total time spent by the animal in the light sector [17].

The O-shaped elevated maze. The maze consisted of a ring with an external diameter of 46 cm and an internal diameter of 34 cm, such that the width of the ring was 6 cm. Opposite segments were enclosed by walls of length 35 cm and height 13 cm along the internal and external diameters. Illumination at the center of the enclosed space was 12 Lx and that of the unenclosed space was 25 Lx. The mouse was

Fig. 4. Analysis of animals' behavior in the open field. *a*) Behavior of γ -knockout mice (%) in normal conditions (60 Lx) and in conditions of strong illumination (450 Lx) as compared with controls (WT); */ identifies data in normal conditions, /* identifies data in conditions of strong illumination; *b*) effects of illumination at 450 Lx (%) on the behavior of control and experimental mice as compared with normal illumination (60 Lx); */ identifies data from control animals, /* identifies data from γ -knockout mice. 1) Total motor activity; 2) movement distance; 3) rate of movement; 4) immobile moment; 5) distance at the perimeter; 6) time at the perimeter; 7, 8, 9) distance, time, and number of visits to the center respectively; 10) number of rearings; 11) total time in rearings; 12) number of glances into holes; 13) total time spent looking into holes. For further details see captions to Figs. 1 and 2.

placed in the center of the enclosed segment and the following parameters were recorded for 5 min: the latent period of departure of all paws into the unenclosed segment, the number of excursions, and the total time spent in the unenclosed segment [6, 26].

The open field test. The animal was placed in the corner of a Tru Scan (CoulBourn Instruments, USA) automatic photosensor apparatus at an illumination of 60 Lx and recordings of vertical and horizontal activity were made over a period of 3 min. The test was repeated after three days at an illumination of 450 Lx [15]. Study parameters are listed in the captions of the appropriate figures.

Standard statistical analysis of the data was performed using Statistica 6. Significant differences were identified using Student's *t* test for independent variables; in addition, results from the open field test were also analyzed using the nonparametric Mann–Whitney U test.

Animal studies were performed in compliance with the “Regulations for laboratory practice in the Russian Federation,” 2003.

RESULTS

The novel cell test. Minute-by-minute investigative activity is shown in Fig. 1. The number of rearings recorded for γ -synuclein knockout mice was significantly greater than that in the wild-type (WT) control group but only dur-

ing the first 3 min of the test (by 58%, $p = 0.0002$, in the first minute, by 47%, $p = 0.0002$, in the second minute, and by 37%, $p = 0.02$, in the third minute).

The dark-light chamber test. The results of studies of animals in the dark-light chamber are presented in Fig. 2. A significant difference in the behavior of animals of the experimental groups was seen in only one parameter – the latent period of excursions into the light sector of the chamber (Fig. 2, *a*). In γ -synuclein knockout mice, this latent period was 95% greater ($p = 0.0038$) than that in WT mice. During testing, γ -synuclein knockout mice made the same number of excursions into the light sector (Fig. 2, *b*) and remained in this sector for the same amount of time (Fig. 2, *c*) as mice of the control group.

The O-shaped elevated maze. Results obtained by testing animals in the O-shaped elevated maze are presented in Fig. 3. The behavior of γ -synuclein knockout mice was significantly different from that of WT animals in terms of all three parameters. Thus, the latent period (Fig. 3, *a*) of excursions of γ -synuclein knockout mice into the unenclosed segment was 74% less ($p < 0.00001$) than that in control animals. The mutant animals also showed more frequent excursions from the enclosed sector than controls (a mean of 5.7 vs. 0.7 excursions, respectively, $p = 0.017$; Fig. 3, *b*) and spent more time in the unenclosed segment (a mean of 42 vs. 2.7 sec, $p = 0.0003$; Fig. 3, *c*).

The open field test. Experimental animals (eight γ -synuclein knockout mice and eight wild-type mice) were test-

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ed twice, with an interval of 72 h between tests. The first test addressed behavior in the lighting conditions to which the animals are accustomed, while the second addressed behavior in conditions of stress induced by an increase in illumination in the experimental chamber to 450 Lx. The test results are presented in Fig. 4. Both tests showed differences in the behavior of mutant animals and wild-type animals (Fig. 4, *a*). There were also differences and the extent of effect of the increased illumination level on the behavior of the animals with different genotypes (Fig. 4, *b*). On testing of the animals in their normal lighting conditions, the frequency of looking into holes in γ -synuclein knockout mice was significantly lower than that in WT mice (decreased by 45%, $p = 0.049$, *t* test; $p = 0.046$, U test).

Numerous differences in the behavior of the animals of the experimental groups were seen in conditions of increased illumination: the time spent by γ -synuclein knockout mice at the periphery of the experimental field was 62% ($p = 0.037$, *t* test; $p = 0.063$, U test), and the time spent in the center and the number of visits to the center were 196% ($p = 0.043$, *t* test; $p = 0.084$, U test) and 63% ($p = 0.033$, *t* test; $p = 0.037$, U test) of the corresponding values for wild-type animals. In conditions of increased illumination, the “immobile moment” (absence of movements within the discrete space of the apparatus) increased significantly both in wild-type animals (by 39%, $p = 0.045$, *t* test; $p = 0.018$, U test) and in γ -synuclein knockout animals; the extents of changes in this parameter were identical in the two groups ($p > 0.05$, *t* test). Stress induced by increased illumination had different effects on the two types of investigative behavior in the mice – looking into holes and vertical rearings. As compared with values seen in conditions of normal illumination, there were synchronous reductions in both the number of rearings, by 52% ($p = 0.024$, *t* test; $p = 0.015$, U test) in knockout mice and by 42% ($p = 0.04$, *t* test; $p = 0.025$, U test) in wild-type mice, and in the duration of rearings, by 51% ($p = 0.02$, *t* test; $p = 0.035$, U test) in the γ -synuclein knockout group and by 52% ($p = 0.02$, *t* test; $p = 0.025$, U test) in WT mice. At the same time, the number of glances and the duration of glancing into holes in conditions of increased illumination were sharply decreased in WT mice – by 69% ($p = 0.007$, *t* test; $p = 0.022$, U test) and 57% ($p = 0.043$, *t* test; $p = 0.055$, U test) respectively – and remained unaltered in γ -synuclein knockout animals. There was also a tendency to an increase in the time spent by γ -synuclein knockout mice in the center of the experimental field – 149% ($p = 0.049$, *t* test; $p = 0.08$, U test) of the value in normal illumination conditions, while no such tendency was seen in the WT group.

DISCUSSION

The current study sought to answer the question of whether γ -synuclein is involved in regulating behavior asso-

ciated with the responses of animals to changes in the environmental content (novelty, stress situation). The concrete task was to evaluate the levels of anxiety and investigative activity in γ -synuclein knockout mice.

On analysis of results from the *novel cage* test, which was used to study orientational-investigative behavior [11, 18], it should be noted that increased orientational activity in γ -synuclein knockout mice, apparent as a significant increase in the number of rearings, was characteristic only of the first and second minutes in the novel conditions, the subsequent behavior of the mutant animals in this test being no different from that of wild-type animals.

Orientalional-investigative behavior in animals depends on the activity of many neural networks and brain systems, so a multitude of explanations for this effect can be suggested. At the same time, considering the extensive evidence for the involvement of synucleins in the processes of synthesis, degradation, exocytosis, and reuptake of neurotransmitters, particularly in relation to dopamine and other catecholamines, in presynaptic neuron terminals [30] on the one hand, and the important role of catecholaminergic systems in orientational-investigative activity on the other, the most likely explanation appears to consist of altered activity of catecholaminergic neurotransmission in the neuron populations involved in this behavior. Further detailed studies of the function of γ -synuclein in different types of synapses and orientational-investigative behavior in γ -synuclein knockout animals in combination with pharmacological modulators of the catecholaminergic systems are required for this suggestion to be verified.

There is some difficulty in interpreting the results obtained in the *dark-light chamber* at this stage of the investigation. Measures such as the number of excursions into the light sector and the time spent in the light sector were identical for the two study groups. At the same time, the latent period of excursions to the light sector in γ -synuclein knockout mice was significantly increased, which contradicts the results obtained in other tests indicating that the absence of γ -synuclein does not affect motor activity (see Fig. 4 and [25]) and stimulates orientational-investigative activity in knockout animals. We suggest that the increase in the latent period can be explained by fear in γ -synuclein knockout mice before going through the relatively narrow corridor connecting the dark chamber with the light sector.

Indirect support for this suggestion was obtained from analysis of the behavior of γ -synuclein knockout mice in the *O-shaped elevated maze*, which assesses the level of situational anxiety in animals [16, 26]. The test results identified a reduction in the latent period of transferring to the unenclosed segment for γ -synuclein knockout mice, evidencing decreased situational anxiety compared with WT mice. The notable increase in the number of excursions to the unenclosed segment of the maze may be due to decreased situational anxiety or increased orientational-investigative activity in mutant animals. At the same time, both the decrease

in the latent period of excursions and the long duration of time spent by γ -synuclein knockout mice in the unenclosed segment of the maze may be evidence for avoidance of the enclosed segment of the maze which, like the *dark-light chamber*, is a narrow corridor, and attempts to leave it. This behavior is not typical of mice and other rodents, which are characterized by a tendency to stay in contact with the chamber walls in a novel context (thymotaxis). Testing of mice in the *open field* in conditions of normal illumination revealed no differences in the behavior of γ -synuclein knockout mice and wild-type mice, with the exception of one parameter – a decrease (by 45%) in the number of glances into holes by mutant animals. As glancing into holes is regarded as a manifestation of orientational-investigative activity, this result contradicts the results described above from the *novel cage* and *O-shaped elevated maze* tests. However, considering the possibility of weakening of thymotaxis and the preference of γ -synuclein knockout mice for closed spaces, it can be suggested that even when actively investigating the new environment, these animals may also avoid investigating closed spaces such as holes.

Stress induced by increased illumination at the second stage of testing mice in the *open field* should, in our view, produce minor and latent changes in the behavior of mutant mice. This suggestion was verified. In conditions of increased illumination, there was a tendency to an increase in the total time spent by γ -synuclein knockout mice in the center of the experimental field as compared with these values for WT mice, which points to a decrease in anxiety in the mutant animals [19, 23]. This is also evidenced by the fact that freezing reactions, typical of wild-type mice placed in stressful conditions [9], were virtually absent in γ -synuclein knockout mice, for which the “immobile moment” parameter was identical in normal and increased illumination.

In addition, the number of glances into holes, which decreased sharply in conditions of increased illumination in wild-type animals, remained unchanged in γ -synuclein knockout animals. The lack of an inhibitory effect of increased illumination on investigative activity is evidence for decreased situational anxiety in conditions of marked single-episode stress [5, 23]. Thus, we can come to the conclusion that γ -synuclein knockout mice are less anxious than control mice.

CONCLUSIONS

The present studies revealed significant differences in the behavior of mice lacking γ -synuclein from the behavior of wild-type mice. We suggest that the absence of γ -synuclein leads to:

increased orientational-investigative reactions to a novel context in the *novel cage* and *O-shaped elevated maze* tests;
decreased situational anxiety in the *O-shaped elevated maze* and *open field* tests in stressful conditions;

avoidance of restricted spaces or weakening of thymotaxis in the *dark-light chamber* and *O-shaped elevated maze* tests.

Thus, the behavior of γ -synuclein knockout mice observed here consists of a balance between increased orientational-investigative activity and the preference for closed spaces, which is facilitated by decreased situational anxiety.

The most likely cause of the behavioral changes seen here in mutant mice was impairment to the molecular mechanism of synaptic plasticity in defined neuron populations lacking γ -synuclein, though only further detailed biochemical, morphological, and behavioral studies of γ -synuclein knockout mice will allow this suggestion to be confirmed or refuted.

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